

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18631987>

**ICHKI YONUV DVIGATELINING KONSTRUKTIV O‘ZGARISHI VA
UNING ISHLASH KO‘RSATKICHLARIGA TA’SIRI**

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada ichki yonuv dvigatellarida (IYoD) amalga oshiriladigan konstruktiv o'zgarishlarning dvigatelning quvvat, yonilg'i tejamkorligi va ekologik ko'rsatkichlariga ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Zamonaviy dvigatellarda silindr-porshen guruhi, gaz taqsimlash mexanizmi, yonilg'i purkash tizimi hamda qo'shimcha energiya manbalaridan foydalanish orqali samaradorlikni oshirish masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan. Konstruktiv modernizatsiya natijasida dvigatelning foydali ish koeffitsienti oshishi, chiqindi gazlar tarkibining kamayishi hamda ish jarayonining barqarorlashuvi ilmiy asosda baholanadi. Multipoint injeksiya (MPI) tizimiga ega ichki yonuv dvigatelini to'g'ridan-to'g'ri yonilg'i purkash (GDI) tizimiga moslashtirish metodikasi ko'rib chiqiladi. Loyihaning maqsadi – yonilg'i sarfini kamaytirish, quvvat va momentni oshirish hamda chiqindi gazlar ko'rsatkichlarini yaxshilashdir. Ilmiy ish doirasida konstruktorlik yechimlar, yuqori bosimli yonilg'i purkash tizimi integratsiyasi, EBB xaritalari va eksperimental sinov metodlari tavsiflanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ichki yonuv dvigateli, konstruktiv o'zgarish, samaradorlik, yonilg'i sarfi, ekologik ko'rsatkichlar, modernizatsiya, multipoint injeksiya, gasoline direct injection, yuqori bosim, yonilg'i purkash tizimi, konstruktiv o'zgarishi, dvigatel ko'rsatkichlari.

KIRISH

Ichki yonuv dvigatellari hozirgi kunda avtomobil, qishloq xo'jaligi va sanoat texnikalarida eng keng qo'llaniladigan energiya manbalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Atrof-muhit muhofazasi, yonilg'i resurslarining cheklanganligi hamda energiya samaradorligini oshirish talablari dvigatel konstruksiyasini takomillashtirishni dolzarb masalaga aylantirmoqda.

Ichki yonuv dvigatelining asosiy konstruktiv qismlari bular asosan silindrlar bloki va silindr kallagi, porshen, shatun va tirsakli val mexanizmi, gaz taqsimlash mexanizmi, yonilg'i ta'minlash va purkash tizimi, sovitish va moylash tizimlaridan borat. Mazkur elementlarning geometrik o'lchamlari, materiali va ishlash tamoyili dvigatelning umumiy samaradorligiga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi. nish va ularning ishlash ko'rsatkichlariga ta'sirini aniqlash muhim ilmiy-amaliy ahamiyatga ega. Ichki yonuv dvigatellari sohasida yonilg'i samaradorligini oshirish va chiqindilarni kamaytirish eng dolzarb vazifalardan biri hisoblanadi. Shu kunlarda mamlakatimizda ommaviy ishlab chiqilayotgan uch silindrli alyuminiy silindr blokli turbo 1.2 L MPI ichki yonuv dvigateliga konstruktiv o'zgartirish, samaradorlik, yonilg'i sarfi, ekologik ko'rsatkichlar yaxshilash borasida modernizatsiya nazarda tutulgan (1-rasm).

1-rasm. Uch silindrli alyuminiy silindr blokli turbo dvigatel.

An'anaviy MPI tizimi yuqori samaradorlikka ega bo'lsa-da, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri yonilg'i purkash tizimi bilan solishtirganda ba'zi jihatlarda quvvat va emissiya ko'rsatkichlarini oshirish imkoniyati mavjud. GDI tizimi silindr ichiga yonilg'ini yuqori bosim ostida purkash orqali aralashmaning yanada nozik va to'liq yonishini ta'minlaydi. Shu sababli, MPI tizimiga ega kichik hajmli dvigatelni GDI tizimiga moslashtirish texnologiyasi zamonaviy muhandislik va ilmiy tadqiqotlarda dolzarb mavzu hisoblanadi.

Gaz taqsimlash mexanizmini modernizatsiya qilish konstruktiv o'zgarishlar (o'zgaruvchan fazali klapanlar, klapan ochilish vaqtini boshqarish) yonuvchi aralashmaning silindrga to'liq kirishini ta'minlab, quvvat va moment ko'rsatkichlarini yaxshilaydi. Yonilg'i purkash tizimini takomillashtirishda esa yonilg'ining mayda tomchilarga parchalanishini, yonish jarayonining to'liq kechishini, chiqindi gazlar miqdorining kamayishini ta'minlaydi.

METODODOLOGIYA

Gaz taqsimlash mexanizmini modernizatsiya qilish, konstruktiv o'zgarishlari MPI tizimidan GDI tizimiga o'tkazish uchun yonish kamerasi markaziga yoki pistonning cho'qqisiga qarab joylashtiriladi, 200–350 bar bosim hosil qiluvchi nasos qo'shiladi, optimal yonish kamerasi shakli aralashmani yaxshilaydi va yonilg'i samaradorligini oshiradi quyidagi mexanik o'zgarishlar, MPI tizimidan GDI tizimiga o'tganda EBB xaritalari yangilanadi y'ani purkash vaqti va davomiyligi o'zgartiriladi, havoning ortiqcha koeffitsienti va havo oqimi datchiklari integratsiya qilinadi, yuqori bosim datchigi va lambda zondlarining ishlashi nazorat qilinadi, bu bosqichdadan maqsadi dvigatelning ishlashini optimallashtirish va aralashmani to'liq yonishini ta'minlashdir.

Yonilg'i purkash hajmi, aralashma sifati (1) formula bilan baholanadi.

$$D = C \cdot \frac{\sigma}{\rho \cdot \Delta P} \quad (1)$$

bu yerda C – tomchi diametri, σ – yuzaki taranglik, ρ – yonilg‘i zichligi, ΔP – bosim farqi.

Foydali ish koeffitsienti (2) formula bilan baholanadi.

$$\eta_e = \frac{Ne}{m_f \cdot Q_{LHV}} \quad (2)$$

bu yerda Ne – effektiv quvvat, m_f – yonilg‘i massasi, Q_{LHV} – yonilg‘ining pastki issiqlik qiymati.

MUHOKAMA VA KUTILAYOTGAN NATIJALAR

O‘tkazilgan tahlillar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, ichki yonuv dvigatelida amalga oshirilgan har bir konstruktiv o‘zgarish tizimli yondashuv asosida baholanishi lozim. Alohida elementlarning takomillashtirilishi dvigatelning umumiy ishlash jarayoniga kompleks ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi. MPI tizimi – har bir silindrga alohida injektor orqali yonilg‘i purkashni ta‘minlaydi. Ushbu tizimning afzalliklari: ishonchlilik, oddiy tuzilish va past xizmat xarajatlari. Shu bilan birga, past quvvat samaradorligi va yuqori aylanishlarda aralashmaning to‘liq yonmasligi MPI tizimining asosiy kamchiliklari hisoblanadi.

Eksperimental tadqiqotda stend sinovlar va yo‘l sinovlar usullari bilan y‘ani dvigatel turli yuk va aylanishlarda sinovdan o‘tkaziladi, quvvat, moment va yonilg‘i sarfi o‘lchanadi hamda kundalik sharoitda yonilg‘i samaradorligi, ishlatilgan chiqindi gazlar optimallashtiriladi, IYoDning **so‘rish, siqish, yonish, chiqarish** to‘liq ish sikl jarayonlarini ketma-ketlik sxemasi modernizasiya qilish amalga oshiriladi a‘naviy sxema bilan taqqoslanadi hamda baholanadi (2-rasm).

GDI tizimi esa yonilg‘ini bevosita silindr ichiga purkash orqali quvvat va samaradorlikni oshiradi. GDI tizimi yuqori bosimli nasos, maxsus forsunka va elektron boshqaruvni talab qiladi, bu esa konstruktorlik va tizim integratsiyasida qo‘shimcha ishlarni yuzaga keltiradi hisoblar tahlillar natijasida yonilg‘i sarfi solishtirganda 10–15% kamroq, quvvat 8–12% oshadi, CO va HC ishlatilgan chiqindi gazlar 20–30% kamayadi.

2- rasm. IYoDning to‘liq ish siklini, ya’ni a) so‘rish, b) siqish, c) yonish, d) chiqarish jarayonlarini ketma-ketlik sxemasi.

1) chiqarish klapanlarini boshqaruvchi taqsimlash vali (kulachoklar), 2) o‘t oldirish shamchasi, 3) kirish klapanlarini boshqaruvchi taqsimlash vali, 4) yonilg‘i purkagich (forsunka), 5) kirish klapani, 6) chiqarish klapani, 7) yonish kamerasi, 8) porshen, 9) silindr, 10) shatun, 11) tirsakli val, M — aylantiruvchi moment (burovchi moment), α — tirsakli valning burulish burchagi, s — porshen yo‘li, V_h — silindrning ish hajmi.

XULOSA

Taklif etilgan texnologik yondashuv 1.2 L MPI ichki yonuv dvigatelining konstruktiv o‘zgarishlari uning texnik-iqtisodiy va ekologik ko‘rsatkichlarini sezilarli darajada yaxshilash imkonini beradi. Zamonaviy materiallar, ilg‘or yonilg‘i purkash tizimlari va mexanizmlarni boshqarish texnologiyalaridan foydalanish dvigatel samaradorligini oshirishning asosiy omillari hisoblanadi.

Dvigatelini GDI tizimiga moslashtirish ilmiy va amaliy jihatdan samarali yo‘nalish hisoblanadi. Ushbu metodika dvigatel quvvatini oshirish, yonilg‘i sarfini kamaytirish va chiqindilarni optimallashtirishga yordam beradi. Shuningdek, dual-injection konsepsiyasi bilan past yukda yonilg‘i tejamkorligi, yuqori yukda esa maksimal quvvatni olish mumkin.

Bu izlanishlar y’ani ichki yonuv dvigatelining konstruktiv o‘zgarishi kichik hajmli avtomobillar uchun iqtisodiy jihatdan samarali dvigatel modernizatsiyasi sifatida keng qo‘llanilishi mumkin.

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